

Blooming Plant by Bloom and Plant

Table S1. Linear least square regressions for the data in Figure 1 that contains *Degree-days, soil temperature, total water applied, N fertilization, pathogen infestation level, and vapor pressure deficit* during the growing season for fall-planted common wheat versus *year* at six Californian locations where field trials were conducted.

Parameter	Location	Slope	Intercept	r^2
Degree-days	Delta	3.2691	-5822	0.0727
	Imperial	8.4973	-15652	0.3597
	Kern	2.0383	-3232	0.0351
	Kings	4.0883	-7348	0.0906
	North	1.8094	-2883	0.0260
	UCD	4.8974	-9081	0.1071
Soil temperature	Delta	0.0244	-37.65	0.1041
	Imperial	0.0094	-4.665	0.0132
	Kern	0.0333	-54.648	0.0641
	Kings	0.0424	-73.375	0.093
	North	-0.0162	42.91	0.0166
	UCD	0.0144	18.509	0.0101
Total water applied	Delta	0.0087859	-17.117	0.2323
	Imperial	0.016597	-32.407	0.5411
	Kern	0.0007312	-0.6623	0.0009
	Kings	-0.0068206	14.331	0.108
	North	-0.0093402	19.287	0.1188
	UCD	-0.0054087	11.519	0.1025
N fertilization	Delta	1.3473	-2655	0.0995
	Imperial	6.609	13044	0.6970
	Kern	1.7780	-3388	0.0246
	Kings	1.5644	3282	0.0410
	North	0.9277	1956	0.0389
	UCD	2.1899	-4290	0.2408
Pathogen infestation	Delta	0.0182	-34.664	0.0395
	Imperial	0.0	1.0	1.000
	Kern	0.0127	-24.023	0.0249
	Kings	0.0389	-76.248	0.1806
	North	0.0346	-67.579	0.1019
	UCD	0.0251	-48.390	0.074
VPD	Delta	1.4137	-2542.8	0.0234
	Imperial	18.357	-36013	0.7207
	Kern	1.8538	-3405.5	0.060
	Kings	1.3753	-2446.1	0.0167
	North	1.4137	-2542.8	0.0223
	UCD	4.3149	-8354.7	0.239

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Table S2. Coefficients (Coef.), intercepts (Int.), and probabilities (p) for the influence of *year* in generalized least squares models of *grain yield* (kg ha⁻¹), *grain protein content*, and *grain protein yield* (kg ha⁻¹) for subsets of the data that contained one of six *locations* in California and all six check *cultivars* or that contained one of six check *cultivars* and all six *locations*. These values are used to construct the lines shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The columns labeled Int. show the value of the regression in 1985.

				Grain Yield			Protein %			Protein Yield		
Location	Cultivar	Years	n	Coef.	Int.	p	Coef. $\times 10^{-4}$	Int.	p	Coef.	Int.	p
Delta	6 cultivars	85–19	122	-108.4	7728	0.0002	3.74	0.113	0.27	-9.79	855	0.01
Imperial	6 cultivars	90–18	69	-92.4	9564	<0.0001	-2.68	0.134	0.13	-14.26	1283	<0.0001
Kern	6 cultivars	86–19	141	-0.18	6832	0.99	-1.30	0.132	0.44	-1.01	904	0.72
Kings	6 cultivars	88–18	132	-28.9	7061	0.29	-0.41	0.131	0.83	-4.07	918	0.23
North	6 cultivars	89–19	152	-55.6	6869	0.022	7.38	0.104	<0.001	-1.29	705	0.69
UCD	6 cultivars	85–19	138	-38.0	6665	0.18	-2.41	0.130	0.04	-7.10	874	0.03
6 locations	Anza	85–17	171	-51.8	7155	0.0004	-2.21	0.118	0.10	-6.92	832	<0.0001
6 locations	Blanca Grande	01–19	101	48.0	5712	0.10	-3.98	0.139	0.14	3.97	796	0.37
6 locations	Express	88–13	126	-79.0	7554	<0.0001	-1.99	0.135	0.31	-11.15	1008	<0.0001
6 locations	Klasic	85–03	86	-177.9	8843	<0.0001	-0.02	0.124	0.99	-24.37	1115	<0.0001
6 locations	Serra	85–04	91	-160.2	8541	<0.0001	1.32	0.119	0.67	-17.64	1001	<0.0001
6 locations	Yecora Rojo	85–19	179	-55.1	6864	0.0007	-0.16	0.130	0.92	-7.44	894	0.01

Fig. S1. Monthly average atmospheric CO₂ concentrations (ppm) measured at Vaira Ranch in the foothills of central California (Ma et al., 2007) or at the Mauna Loa Observatory on the big island of Hawaii (Lindsey, 2020). The higher seasonal CO₂ variation in California derives from higher primary productivity.

Fig. S2. Changes in wheat grain protein content (%) versus year of registration in field trials of elite winter wheat cultivars released during the past 50 years in western Europe, particularly Germany (Voss-Fels et al., 2019). Plots received 220 kg ha⁻¹ N fertilizer and fungicide or no fungicide or 110 kg ha⁻¹ N fertilizer and no fungicide. Shown are linear regressions labelled with slopes, intercepts, and correlations squared.